

Portuguese regional ionosphere maps – PRIMA

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Project report

Abstract

Instituto de Astrofísica e Ciências do Espaço at the University of Coimbra (IA-UC) has a small group (and only one working permanently on this subject in Portugal) of researchers working in the area of ionospheric studies. To the moment no systematic studied of ionospheric response to space weather disturbances (i.e., disturbance of the solar and magnetospheric origin) were performed for Portuguese regions, neither Continental nor Insular (Azores and Madeira). One of the reasons is the lack of good quality data. Thus, the compilation of a database of ionospheric parameters including the total electron content (TEC) for the whole Portuguese region will be a necessary step for any study: data analysis, development of regional models to predict ionospheric response to different space weather events, development of regional ionospheric maps or other products that can be used by national service providers and end users.

Significant amount of the GNSS data from the Portuguese geodetic GNSS networks (as RAEGE-Az and RENEP) cannot be added to a such database because these data are available only as GNSS raw or pre-processed data formats (e.g., RINEX) and have to be converted to TEC data. Unfortunately, IA-UC team members did not have sufficient experience in such data processing. The PITHIA-TNA call was a perfect opportunity for the IA-UC team members to obtain new knowledge working in collaboration with the UPC-IonSAT team that has extensive experience in collecting and processing GNSS data from different GNSS systems.

As a result of the collaboration with UPC-IonSAT team, the IA-UC team obtained necessary knowledge and software to process the files and significantly enlarged the Portuguese ionospheric parameters database using high quality data from the Azores Archipelago. The new data allowed to perform comparative studies of ionospheric disturbances observed during geomagnetic storms at different longitudinal sectors.

Also, the UPC-IonSAT team agreed to support the IA-UC team in a planned development of RIMs for Portugal using data from RENEP and RAEGE-Az GNSS networks. The IA-UC will submit a project to a Portuguese national call for research projects in summer 2023 with UPC-IonSAT team members as advisors/consultants of the project.

Objective

In January 2022 an exploratory project PRIME - Portuguese regional ionosphere Model (FCT EXPL/CTA-MET/0677/2021) funded by the Portuguese national foundation FCT (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia), started at the Instituto de Astrofísica e Ciências do Espaço at the University of Coimbra (IA-UC) led by A. Morozova (PI) and T. Barata (co-PI). The PRIME

project purses 2 goals: (1) to study differences in the ionospheric conditions between the Continental and Insular (Azores and Madeira archipelagos) Portuguese territories, and (2) to develop a prototype for a regional model to forecast ionospheric total electron content (TEC) both for the Continental and Insular Portugal. In turn, the 1st goal of the PRIME project consists of 2 work lines: the 1st line is aimed at creation of a unified database containing GNSS TEC observations for the whole Portuguese region. The 2nd work line, performed in parallel, consists of the analysis of this database to understand TEC variations at different latitudes (Continental Portugal vs Madeira) and longitudes (Azores vs Continental Portugal). The results of this analysis will be used in the frame of the PRIME project to adjust the prototype model of TEC variations to model and forecast TEC for different Portuguese regions.

Creation of the good quality database of ionospheric parameters for Portuguese regions is a crucial for the PRIME success. The core of this database consists of TEC and SI (scintillation indices) data obtained during one of our previous projects – SWAIR (Space Weather impact on GNSS service for Air Navigation, ESA Small Artes 20). During that project a geodetic receiver was installed in the Lisbon airport area. This receiver used a SCINDA software that calculate TEC and SI data (Barlyaeva et al., 2020a,b; Morozova et al., 2022a,b). Also, to fill the database we use data available for the Portuguese region at OA databases (e.g., Royal Observatory of Belgium, GNSS Research Group, ROB, http://gnss.be/Atmospheric_Maps/ionospheric_maps.php).

However, we want to enlarge our database with data generated by two national networks of geodetic GNSS receivers: RAEGE-Az (Rede Atlântica de Estações Geodinâmicas e Espaciais - Azores Association, <https://raege-az.pt/en/>) and RENEP (Rede Nacional de Estações Permanentes GNSS, <https://renep.dgterritorio.gov.pt/>). These two networks cover both the Continental (RENEP) and Insular (RENEP and RAEGE-Az) regions of Portugal – see Fig. 1.

Figure 1. RENEP (green) and RAEGE-Az (yellow) networks of GNSS receivers: all regions (left) and Continental only (right).

Advantage of the inclusion of the RENEP and RAEGE-Az data to the database is that each of these networks provides a homogenous data (same type of the receivers, same pre-processing procedures) with an easy access. On the other hand, the data format used by these networks are RINEX 2.11 and RINEX 3.0, respectively, which need further file processing to obtain TEC values. Unfortunately, IA-UC team members did not have sufficient experience in such data processing. The PITHIA-TNA call (project **PRIMA**) was a perfect opportunity for us to obtain

new knowledge working in collaboration with the UPC-IonSAT team that has extensive experience in collecting and processing GNSS data from different GNSS systems.

Another goal of **PRIMA** was to study possibilities of development of Portuguese regional TEC maps (PT-RIM) using data from national GNSS networks giving special attention to the oceanic areas near the Portuguese archipelagos of Azores and Madeira. This RIMs, together with currently developing models to forecast TEC using space weather parameters as predictors (Morozova et al., 2020, 2022c,d) are intended later to be turned into products that can be used by national service providers and end users.

Project process

Initially the **PRIMA** project has been planned to start in February 2022 and to end in July 2022, however due to the teaching load of the members of UPC-IonSAT team and other activities of members of both teams, it was rescheduled to May-December 2022, and because the in-person visit of A. Morozova to UPC-IonSat was re-scheduled to the end of November 2022, the actual work continued as well in January 2023.

The pre-visit activities included collection of test files from the RAEGE-Az network (IA-UC team), tests made with these files by the UPC-IonSAT members; also, the UPC-IonSAT team provided the IA-UC team with manuals and publications that describe the UPC-IonSAT software, data processing and other technical procedures. Also, the UPC-IonSAT team started to develop codes compatible to software and operating systems used by the IA-UC team.

During the in-person visit the algorithms for TEC calculations and calibration used by the UPC-IonSAT team were explained in detail. Processing of the RINEX-to-TEC files was tested on the files provided by RAEGE-Az and plans for further research work were made.

Also, during the discussion it was decided that since RAEGE-Az data are included in the EPOS (European Plate Observing System, <https://gnssdata-epos.oca.eu/> or <ftp://epncb.oma.be/pub/obs>) data base they are of no interest for the UPC node as a new data source. Also, the RAEGE-Az network is too small to be used to construct Portuguese RIMs, but data from RENEP seems to be a promising data source for PT-RIMs, and the work should be done later in the frame of another project, e.g., another national (FCT) funded research project.

The post-visit activities included conversion of RAEGE-Az files collected for selected time intervals (geomagnetic storms) and analysis of similarities and differences in the response of the ionosphere over the Continental and Insular areas: Lisbon vs Furnas/S. Miguel island (RENEP) and Sta. Maria island (RAEGE-Az). This study allowed us to verify RENEP and RAEGE-Az data between themselves and also to verify RENEP data vs data derived from ROB maps.

Data

The data used in this work are RINEX 3.0 file prepared by RAEGE-Az for the EPOS database from a GNSS geodetic receiver at the Sta. Maria island of the Azores archipelago (36.8° N, 26.6°W) obtained with 30 sec cadence. These files were processed and calibrated using codes developed by the UPC-IonSAT team (see, e.g., Hernández-Pajares et al., 2011, 2018). The code

read RINEX 3.0 files to obtain ionospheric (geometry-free) combination of dual-frequency carrier phases L1-L2, download satellites RINEX 3 broadcast ephemeris files in SP3 format to calculate non-calibrated sTEC (i.e. affected by the carrier phase bias) from each of the available satellite and receiver, and to use UQRG GIMs to calibrate sTEC. The output files contain detailed information on the time of observations, receiver coordinates and coordinates of the ionosphere pierce points positions, calibrated sTEC and the mapping function to be used to calculate vTEC, SD of sTEC, etc. Thus, these output (processed) files can be used for different type of analysis: variations of vTEC during certain time periods and for different GNSS constellations, for certain elevations and azimuthal directions etc.

Figure 2 shows an example of vTEC variations obtained for Sta. Maria RAEGE-Az station for May 26 – 31, 2017 and the average quiet daily vTEC variations for this time interval.

Figure 2. vTEC of Sta. Maria (black solid lines) for May 26 – 31, 2017. Grey area marks the day of a geomagnetic storm.

Analyses and Results

A case study was performed using the processed files to study an effect of a geomagnetic storm on the ionosphere for two locations, Portugal Continental (Lisbon) and Azores (Sta. Maria). These locations have approximately same latitude (39°N vs 36.8°N, respectively) but separated by about 18° in longitude (9°W vs 26.6°W, respectively). In this study the data for Lisbon were obtained from ROB ionospheric maps (Bergeot et al., 2014) for a grid point most close to Lisbon. The RAEGE-Az vTEC was calculated using all available satellites and ROB maps are constructed using only GPS satellites.

A geomagnetic storm took place on May 28, 2017, with $Dst_{min} = -125$ nT observed at 07:00 UTC (see Fig. 3). As one can see from Fig. 3 the storm lasted for about 1 day, but small geomagnetic disturbances were observed on the day after the storm as well, seen both in Dst (~50 nT) and in AE (50- ~100 nT) indices.

Figures 4 and 5 show variations of vTEC and Δ TEC (difference between the observed vTEC and the quiet daily vTEC variation) for Lisbon (red solid lines) and Sta. Maria (black solid

lines) during the time interval May 26 – 31, 2017. As one can see, both locations show very similar behavior of vTEC: a negative ionospheric storm during the first day of the geomagnetic storm (-7 TECu) and a positive ionospheric storm on the next day (+10 TECu). For both days the TEC variations exceed the 2σ threshold.

Figure 3. Dst (black) and AE (red) variations during a geomagnetic storm on May 28, 2017. Grey area marks the day of the storm. Vertical red lines mark Dst minimum on May 28 and the time of vTEC peak around 08:30 UTC on May 30.

Figure 4. vTEC for Lisbon (red solid lines) and Sta. Maria (black solid lines) for May 26 – 31, 2017. Grey area marks the day of a geomagnetic storm. Vertical red line mark Dst minimum on May 28.

Another interesting feature of TEC variations is a sharp peak of about 8 TECu ($> 2\sigma$) observed at Lisbon (eastern part of the studied region) around 08:15-08:30 UTC which corresponds to a

very small ($< 1\sigma$) but still prominent peak observed at the same time at Sta. Maria. This peak does not correspond to any significant geomagnetic activity (see. Fig. 3). To prove that this feature is not an artifact of ROB maps interpolation procedure and to further study its origin as well as to validate the RAEGE-Az data, data from the RENEP network were used. To validate the RAEGE-Az data we used the data from FRNS station on the S. Miguel Island (37.8°N, 25.3°W); to validate the ROB data we used RENEP station IGP0 (38.7°N, 9.15°W). All the locations are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 5. Δ TEC for Lisbon (red solid lines) and Sta. Maria (black solid lines) for May 26 – 31, 2017. Horizontal lines show $\pm 2\sigma$ range for Δ TEC. Vertical red lines mark Dst minimum on May 28 and the time of vTEC peak around 08:30 UTC on May 30.

Figure 6. Stations used to analyze TEC variations: ROB and IGP0 on the Continent and RAEGE and FRNS on the Azores.

Figures 7-8 shows variations of vTEC and Δ TEC for these four locations. First of all, all four series show remarkable consistence (except for the variations observed at IGP0 on May 27, 2017, which will be verified later using data from another RENEP station nearby). The amplitude and temporary features of Δ TEC variations caused by the geomagnetic storm on

May 28, 2017, are the same for all stations. On the other hand, the TEC variations seen at the morning hours of May 30, 2017, are distinctly different between the Continental and Azorean stations: a peak in $vTEC$ variations is clearly seen in all four series around 08:15-08:30, however its amplitude is very small at the western (Azores) part of the studied regions and is no less than 2σ in its eastern part (Lisbon).

Figure 7. $vTEC$ for Lisbon: ROB (red solid lines) and IGPO (red dashed lines), and Azores islands Sta. Maria (black solid lines) and S. Miguel/FRNS (black dashed lines).

Figure 8. ΔTEC for Lisbon: ROB (red solid lines) and IGPO (red dashed lines), and Azores islands Sta. Maria (black solid lines) and S. Miguel/FRNS (black dashed lines).

The origin of this peak observed at the morning hours of May 30, 2017, is not clear yet. It can be related, for example, to (possibly geomagnetic storm associated) traveling ionospheric disturbances, TID, as shown in Jonah et al., 2018, or to plasma bubbles effect, as shown in Batista et al., 2012. An analysis of TEC variations seen in this regions during other geomagnetic storms is currently performed.

The added value gained from the TNA

The participation in the PITHIA TNA allowed the IA-UC team to acquire knowledge and obtain software and technical support from the UPC-IonSAT team for the extraction of the information on TEC from RINEX 3.0 files. This new know-how significantly improved the quality of the data used by IA-UC team and enhanced the area covered by the potentially available ionospheric data, including such regions as the Azorean Archipelago and Madiera. A paper that includes an analysis of the newly obtained TEC series during geomagnetic storms is in preparation to be submitted to *Atmosphere* SI until March 31, 2023.

Also, we hope that future collaboration with the UPC-IonSAT team will result in development by the IA-UC team of a new product – PT-RIMs based on the data from the Portuguese networks of geodetic receivers.

Summary

The PITHIA TNA project **PRIMA** allowed the IA-UC team to essentially improve its knowledge of the processing of files generated by GNSS receivers (RINEX 3.0) and, thus, to have an access to the wide range of data generated by the national networks of geodetic receivers (RENEP and RAEGE-Az) located both in the Continental and Insular parts of Portugal.

Preliminary analysis allowed us, first of all, to validate these data sets: e.g., RENEP data vs data provided by ROB, and RENEP vs RAEGE-Az data, and later to make a comparative study of the behavior of the ionosphere over the Continental and Insular parts of Portugal during geomagnetic storms. The similarity and differences in the TEC variations obtained for different regions will improve our understanding of the ionosphere behavior at the middle and low-to-middle latitudes.

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